

Mobilizing microbial data

ELIXIR All hands meeting - Thessaloniki Greece 2025

Bérénice Batut (FR) - Microbiome Community

Erik Hjerde (NO) - Pathogen Data Focus Group

Practical information

Time (EEST)	Subject
11:00	Welcome and introduction Speaker: Erik & Bérénice
11:10	Metadata standards in sequence archives: ENA metadata model Speaker: Joana Pauperio (EMBL-EBI)
11:20	Metadata identification - Group work (in parallel) <i>Questions: What is the minimal metadata you need to conduct your studies? Do they exist in checklists? What type of metadata would you feel comfortable to expose prior to publication?</i>
11:45	Short summary Facilitators: Erik & Bérénice
11:50	Harmonisation of clinical terms using Ontomapper <input type="checkbox"/> Speaker: Mark Ibberson (SIB)
12:00	Solutions for metadata improvement - Group work (in parallel)
12:25	Summary Facilitators: Erik & Bérénice

Practical information

List of participants (Please fill in):

First name	Last name	Contact email	Institution	Country	City	ORCID*
Erik	Hjerde	erik.hjerde@uit.no	UiT	Norway	Tromsø	0000-0002-6014-1249

Mobilizing microbial data and technical solutions for this

Mobilizing microbial data effectively presents challenges:

Metadata standards

- Lack of harmonization makes it difficult to integrate, compare, and reuse microbial data
- Incomplete or poorly annotated metadata
- Lack of rich metadata for such as outbreak linkage, clinical severity, or antimicrobial treatment history for public health use
- Lack of consensus on minimal metadata requirements for microbiome studies

Technical solutions

- Lack of user-friendly tools
- Fragmented landscape of submission tools, each tailored to specific repositories
- Tools often require manual input, and lack standardized APIs and automation
- Curation is often decoupled from submission tools and performed post hoc by repositories with limited feedback to the data providers.

How can we improve the current situation?

Two group work sessions:

Session I: Metadata identification

- What metadata you need to conduct your studies?
- Would you allow exposure of data prior to publication?

Expected outcomes

- Map willingness to expose data prior to publication
- Map metadata requirements beyond minimal information needed to conduct your studies

Session II: Metadata improvement

- What are common issues found in submitted metadata?
- How can we improve the existing metadata situation?
- Do you have a local or national system (e.g. a data hub) that enable capturing rich metadata that can be reused later?

Expected outcomes

- Possible solutions to improve metadata
 - at submission
 - after submission

What is metadata?

“Data”

“Metadata”

Environment
Compound
Infection
Inhibitor
siRNA
sgRNA
Dose
Time

Sex
Age
Weight
Litter
Genotype
Species
Cell line

Operator
Batch
Plate
Cage
Array
Flowcell
Instrument
Day
Order
Source

Experimental
Treatment
Sampling
Measurement

Metadata needs to be properly structured

Metadata helps make data FAIR

Data should be Findable	<p>F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (DOI)</p> <p>F2. data are described with rich metadata</p> <p>F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes</p> <p>F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource</p>
Data should be Accessible	<p>A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol</p> <p>A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable</p> <p>A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary</p> <p>A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available</p>
Data should be Interoperable	<p>I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.</p> <p>I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles</p> <p>I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data</p>
Data should be Reusable	<p>R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes</p> <p>R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license</p> <p>R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance</p> <p>R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards</p>

Metadata standards in sequence archives: ENA metadata model

Joana Paupério

EMBL-EBI

Background

Open platform for the management, sharing, integration and dissemination of sequence data

- Globally comprehensive scientific record and European node of INSDC
- **Broad scope** covering raw data, through layers of interpretation and context
- **Connectivity** with broader EMBL-EBI resources
- Sequence data **foundation**
- Rich submission, discovery and retrieval **software, tools and services**
- **Support** through Helpdesk and training
- **Management**, sharing, integration and dissemination of sequence data
- **Data coordination** including project-specific data hubs and portals

Archive

Platform

ENA Data model

Sequence data is organised into tiers:

- **Reads:** raw sequence data
- **Assemblies:** reconstructions of actual replicons
- **Annotations:** interpretations of biological function

Annotation and assembly are frequently paired

ENA metadata model

Sample metadata standards

- Sample metadata checklists guided by standards working groups and the communities
 - Keep up with requirements within communities
- Rich standardised metadata facilitates linking to source information
- General minimum requirements (INSDC)
 - Organism information mandatory and linked with NCBI taxonomy
 - INSDC spatiotemporal policy: mandatory provision of collection date & geographic location
 - INSDC missing value reporting

INSDC spatiotemporal metadata – minimum standards update (03-03-2023)

[Home](#) > [News & Announcements](#) > [INSDC spatiotemporal metadata – minimum standards update \(03-03-2023\)](#)

INSDC continues its aim to increase the number of sequences for which the origin of the sample can be precisely located in time and space through harmonisation of accurate geographical annotation and date and time of collection information.

Sample checklists

Minimum amount of information expected to describe biological samples required for registration in ENA

Sample Checklists

There is a minimum amount of information required during ENA sample registration and all samples must conform to a defined checklist of expected metadata values. The most suitable checklist for sample registration depends on the type of the sample.

These sample checklists have been developed to meet the needs of different research communities. Different communities have different requirements on the minimum metadata expected to describe biological samples. For any questions regarding checklists, contact us [here](#).

Filter by accession/name/description/field name

Selected Filters: microbial ✕

Accession	Name	Description
ERC000019	GSC MlxS microbial mat biofilm	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000022	GSC MlxS soil	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000027	ENA Micro B3	Minimum information about a Micro B3 sample. A checklist for reporting metadata of marine microbial samples associated with genomics data. NOTE: Non-genomics data, i.e. oceanographic environmental data and morphology-based biodiversity data, should be submitted to the appropriate National Oceanographic Data Centre according to established reporting practices maintained by oceanographic community experts. Major National Oceanographic Data Centres from countries bordering the North-East Atlantic, and its adjacent seas: the Mediterranean, the Black Sea, the Baltic, the North Sea and the Arctic are listed at http://www.seadatanet.org/Overview/Partners . For the Ocean Sampling Day campaign, non-genomics data shall be reported to the PANGAEA (http://www.pangaea.de/submit/).

Sample checklists

You have selected **GSC MIMAGS**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	tax_id	Text field	None	Taxonomy ID of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database. Entries in the NCBI Taxonomy database have integer taxon IDs. See our tips for sample taxonomy here
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	scientific_name	Text field	None	Scientific name of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database. Scientific names typically follow the binomial nomenclature. For example, the scientific name for humans is Homo sapiens.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_alias	Text field	None	Unique name of the sample. If not selected system will auto generate an unique alias
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_title	Text field	None	Title of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_description	Text field	None	Description of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	metagenomic source		None	The metagenomic source of the sample. This value should contain "metagenome" and be in the taxonomy database e.g. wastewater metagenome or human gut metagenome. Please note "metagenome" alone will not be accepted. Check here for more details on metagenome taxonomy: https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/faq_taxonomy.html#environmental-taxonomic-classifications
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample derived from	Regular expression	None	Reference to parental sample(s) or original run(s) that the assembly is derived from. The referenced samples or runs should already be registered in INSDC. This should be formatted as one of the following. A single sample/run e.g. ERSxxxxxx OR a comma separated list e.g. ERSxxxxxx,ERSxxxxxx OR a range e.g. ERSxxxxxx-ERSxxxxxx
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	project name	Text field	None	Name of the project within which the sequencing was organized

Sample checklists

Add custom field

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Recommended Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	assembly software	Text field	None	Tool(s) used for assembly, including version number and parameters in the format {software};{version};{parameters} e.g. metaSPAdes;3.11.0;kmer set 21,33,55,77,99,121, default parameters otherwise

Optional Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	relationship to oxygen	Permitted values	None	Is this organism an aerobe, anaerobe? Please note that aerobic and anaerobic are valid descriptors for microbial environments
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample collection device	Text field	None	The device used to collect an environmental sample. It is recommended to use terms listed under environmental sampling device (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO) and/or terms listed under specimen collection device (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/GENEPIO_0002094).
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample collection method	Text field	None	The method employed for collecting the sample. Can be provided in the form of a PMID, DOI, url or text.

Sample metadata standards

Biosample: [SAMEA110474009](#)

IS-Seq of IS256 Insertions from a colony originating in a mouse

Biosample: [SAMEA114301107](#)

772f163a-6eb8-4fe9-9fa7-ce70fac1aa8a-asg-maxbin2.067

Organism:	Enterococcus faecalis
Scientific Name:	Enterococcus faecalis
Sample Accession:	SAMEA110474009
Center Name:	UNIVERSITY OF COLORADO DENVER, SCHOOL OF MEDICINE
Sample Alias:	Mouse5_Day16_Rep2
Checklist:	ERC000028
Sample Title:	Mouse 5 Day 16 Replicate 2
ENA-CHECKLIST:	ERC000028
Isolate:	Mouse5_Day16_Rep2
ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC:	2022-08-13T00:19:23Z;2022-08-13
ENA-LAST-UPDATE:	2022-08-13T00:19:23Z;2022-08-13
Host Health State:	healthy
Host Scientific Name:	Mus musculus
Collection Date:	2021-10-06
Geographic Location (Country And/or Sea):	USA
Isolation Source:	Mouse feces plated on BHI with 100 ug/mL gentamicin

Organism:	uncultured Tolumonas sp.
Scientific Name:	uncultured Tolumonas sp.
Sample Accession:	SAMEA114301107
Location:	52.2 N 0.121 E
Center Name:	Tree of Life Programme
Sample Alias:	772f163a-6eb8-4fe9-9fa7-ce70fac1aa8a
Checklist:	ERC000047
Sample Title:	772f163a-6eb8-4fe9-9fa7-ce70fac1aa8a-asg-maxbin2.067
Original Collection Date:	2013
Assembly Software:	metaMDBG
Habitat:	Anoxic culture flask
Host Scientific Name:	Cyclidium porcatum
Original Collection Location:	United Kingdom Dorset Wareham East Stoke East Stoke Fen Nature Reserve
Sample Derived From:	SAMEA114300906
Geographic Location (Longitude):	0.121
Number Of Standard Trnas Extracted:	74
Specimen Id:	UOBC0000070
ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC:	2023-08-24T11:35:35Z;2023-08-24
Identified Bv:	GENOVEVA ESTEBAN WILLIAM LEWIS

ENA metadata model

Experiment metadata

- STUDY: Study accession or unique name (alias)
- SAMPLE: Sample accession or unique name (alias)
- NAME: Unique experiment name
- PLATFORM: [See permitted values](#). Not needed if INSTRUMENT is provided.
- INSTRUMENT: [See permitted values](#)
- INSERT_SIZE: Insert size for paired reads
- LIBRARY_NAME: Library name (optional)
- LIBRARY_SOURCE: [See permitted values](#)
- LIBRARY_SELECTION: [See permitted values](#)
- LIBRARY_STRATEGY: [See permitted values](#)
- DESCRIPTION: free text library description (optional)

Permitted values for library source

- GENOMIC: Genomic DNA (includes PCR products from genomic DNA).
- GENOMIC SINGLE CELL:
- TRANSCRIPTOMIC: Transcription products or non genomic DNA (EST, cDNA, RT-PCR, screened libraries).
- TRANSCRIPTOMIC SINGLE CELL:
- METAGENOMIC: Mixed material from metagenome.
- METATRANSCRIPTOMIC: Transcription products from community targets
- SYNTHETIC: Synthetic DNA.
- VIRAL RNA: Viral RNA.
- OTHER: Other, unspecified, or unknown library source material.

Experiment metadata

You have selected **Fastq File Type**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Show Description

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Field Label	Permitted Value	Description
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample	Sample		Sample alias or accession.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	study	Study		Study alias or accession.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	instrument_model	Instrument model	Permitted values	The sequencing instrument model used in the experiment
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_name	Library name		The name for the library if any.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_source	Library source	Permitted values	The type of source material that is being sequenced.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_selection	Library selection	Permitted values	The method used to select for or against, enrich, or screen the material being sequenced.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_strategy	Library strategy	Permitted values	The sequencing technique intended for this library.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_layout	Library layout	Permitted values	The library layout specifies whether to expect single or paired configuration of reads.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	forward_file_name	Forward file name		Please enter compressed fastq the file name including any subdirectory name
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	forward_file_md5	Forward File checksum		The file MD5 checksum. This field is mandatory if you do not use the Webin File Uploader or upload the checksum using a .md5 file.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	reverse_file_name	Reverse file name		Please enter compressed fastq the file name including any subdirectory name
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	reverse_file_md5	Reverse file checksum		The file MD5 checksum. This field is mandatory if you do not use the Webin File Uploader or upload the checksum using a .md5 file.

ENA metadata model

Analysis metadata

- Dependent on the type of analysis
- Includes mandatory and optional information
- For assemblies:
 - STUDY: Study accession or unique name (alias)
 - SAMPLE: MAG sample accession or unique name (alias)
 - ASSEMBLYNAME: Unique assembly name
 - ASSEMBLY_TYPE: 'Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG)'
 - COVERAGE: The estimated depth of sequencing coverage
 - PROGRAM: The assembly program
 - PLATFORM: The sequencing platform, or comma-separated list of platforms
 - MINGAPLENGTH: Minimum length of consecutive Ns to be considered a gap (optional)
 - MOLECULETYPE: 'genomic DNA', 'genomic RNA' or 'viral cRNA' (optional)
 - DESCRIPTION: Free text description of the genome assembly (optional)
 - RUN_REF: Comma separated list of run accession(s) (optional)

Content enrichment

The Contextual Data Clearinghouse enables extension, correction and improvement of metadata on INSDC records by submission of curations

Contextual Data ClearingHouse (CDCH) OAS 3.0

</ena/clearinghouse/api/v3/api-docs>

This work was funded by ELIXIR, the research infrastructure for life-science data.

[ENA Helpdesk - Website](#)

Servers

▾

Authorize

Contextual Data Clearing House Endpoints for the curation operations

GET /curations

POST /curations

GET /curations/{id}

PATCH /curations/{id}

3rd party curations

Biosample: [SAMEA114318301](#)

a38305d1-0f6d-40d2-b78a-053dcde30fde-asg-bin.95

Organism: [Rhodococcus qingshengii](#)
Scientific Name: [Rhodococcus qingshengii](#)
Sample Accession: [SAMEA114318301](#)
Location: 41.67 N 2.8 E
Center Name: Tree of Life Programme
Sample Alias: a38305d1-0f6d-40d2-b78a-053dcde30fde
Checklist: ERC000047
Sample Title: a38305d1-0f6d-40d2-b78a-053dcde30fde-asg-bin.95
Assembly Software: metaMDBG
Habitat: rocky bottom

Show More

3rd Party Curations

Operation	Attribute Name	Attribute Value	Assertion Method	Assertion Evidences	Provider Name
Add	EEZ-IHO-intersect-name	Spanish part of the Balearic Sea	automatic assertion	automatic assertion , evidence based on logical inference from automatic annotation used in automatic assertion	European Nucleotide Archive
Add	EEZ-IHO-intersect-name	Spanish part of the Balearic Sea	automatic assertion	automatic assertion , evidence based on logical inference from automatic annotation used in automatic assertion	European Nucleotide Archive

General

View: [XML](#)
Download: [XML](#)
Cross References: [Show](#)
3rd Party Curations: [Hide](#)
ORCID Data Claims: [Show](#)
Related ENA Records: [Show](#)

Data

Wgs Files: [Show](#)

Tags

[environment by geolocation](#)

Thank you!

Group work – Metadata

Additional metadata is often generated that is not required for submission but is valuable for downstream analysis, data reuse, and contextual interpretation

1. We want you to help us identify what metadata you need to conduct your studies beyond the mandatory (minimal) elements required by the final repository. Do they exist in checklists?
2. What type of metadata would you feel comfortable to expose prior to publication to allow early discovery of data?

Group work – Metadata

Aim: To identify

Group 1 [Onsite]: Pathogen data from the Pathogens Portal

Facilitators: Erik - Secretary: Espen

Group 2 [Onsite]: Microbiome via example of bee microbiome

Facilitators: Bérénice - Secretary: Eric

Group 3 [Online]: Pathogen data from the Pathogens Portal / or Environmental microbiome

Facilitators: Nikolaos

Group work – Metadata

Tasks: Fill in [table](#) (Not exhaustive – please add more elements in drop downs if needed)

1. As **Data producer** - Submitting data to public repositories
2. As **Data consumer** - Re-using data from public repositories

	Data producer	Data consumer				
	Use case	Data type	Organism group	Scientific application area	Purpose of data production	Public repository for your data
Example 1		Genomic isolates	Bacteria	Human health	AMR gene association studies	ENA
Example 2		Genomic isolates	Bacteria	Human health	AMR gene association studies	ENA
1		Metagenomics				
2		Transcriptomics				
3		Proteomics				
4		Amplicon				
5		MLST				

Swiss Institute of
Bioinformatics

AHM MEETING 2025

ONTOMAPPER

MOBILIZING MICROBIAL DATA WORKSHOP

Mark Ibberson, Lou Götz, Imane Lboukili
Vital-IT group, SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics

04/06/2025

 Naming something correctly is not always obvious!

A simple example - Gender

GENDER Original	GENDER Clean
Male	M
M	M
m	M
Female	F
F	F
f	F
unknown	
na	

Clinical data harmonisation – what do we mean?

Data cleaning

GENDER Original	GENDER Clean
Male	M
M	M
m	M
Female	F
F	F
f	F
unknown	
na	

Standardization or Harmonisation or Mapping

GENDER Clean	Standard Concept	Standard Concept ID
M	gender_concept	8507
F	gender_concept	8532

Identifier we will
use
(e.g. in a database)

In our projects we follow a process

Mapping clinical terms in Excel

Original variable column

Target concept column

One sheet for each OMOP CDM target table

Source Value	Target concept
longer eating syndrome (no - in the present - un the past)	Observation observation_concept_id 4209113 History of binge eating syndrome
History of cancers (no - yes)	Observation observation_concept_id 443392 History of cancers
History of cancers : informations	Observation observation_concept_id 443392 History of cancers : informations
Cardiac history (no - yes)	Observation observation_concept_id 321588 Cardiac history
Cardiac history : informations	Observation observation_concept_id 321588 Cardiac history : informations
compulsive and binge eating (no - yes - DNA)	Observation observation_concept_id 4159146 Compulsive and binge eating
compulsive and binge eating (no - yes - DNA)	Observation observation_concept_id 4159146 Compulsive and binge eating
compulsive and binge eating (no - yes - DNA)	Observation observation_concept_id 4159146 Compulsive and binge eating
compulsive and binge eating (no - yes - DNA)	Observation observation_concept_id 4159146 Compulsive and binge eating
compulsive and binge eating (no - yes - DNA)	Observation observation_concept_id 4159146 Compulsive and binge eating
Oral contraception (0 - 1)	Observation observation_concept_id 4241216 Oral contraception
Oral contraception (0 - 1)	Observation observation_concept_id 4241216 Oral contraception
Oral contraception (0 - 1)	Observation observation_concept_id 4241216 Oral contraception
Oral contraception (0 - 1)	Observation observation_concept_id 4241216 Oral contraception
Oral contraception (0 - 1)	Observation observation_concept_id 4241216 Oral contraception
History of diabetes (no - yes)	Observation observation_concept_id 4188893 History of diabetes
History of diabetes : informations	Observation observation_concept_id 4188893 History of diabetes : informations
number of diet (no - from 1 to 3 - more than 3)	Observation observation_concept_id 4234750 Weight reduction diet
History of disorder of digestive system (no - yes)	Observation observation_concept_id 4188893 History of disorder of digestive system
History of gastroesophageal reflux disease (no - yes)	Observation observation_concept_id 4188893 History of gastroesophageal reflux disease
History of disorder of digestive system (informations)	Observation observation_concept_id 4188893 History of disorder of digestive system (informations)
Eating behavior : rating hunger	Observation observation_concept_id 4125462 Finding of appetite
Eating behavior : rating hunger	Observation observation_concept_id 4125462 Finding of appetite
Eating behavior : rating hunger	Observation observation_concept_id 4125462 Finding of appetite
Eating behavior : rating hunger	Observation observation_concept_id 4125462 Finding of appetite
Eating behavior : rating hunger	Observation observation_concept_id 4125462 Finding of appetite
Eating behavior : rating pleasure	Observation observation_concept_id 4087320 Eating behavior and appetite
Eating behavior : rating pleasure	Observation observation_concept_id 4087320 Eating behavior and appetite
Eating behavior : rating pleasure	Observation observation_concept_id 4087320 Eating behavior and appetite
Eating behavior : rating pleasure	Observation observation_concept_id 4087320 Eating behavior and appetite
Eating behavior : rating pleasure	Observation observation_concept_id 4087320 Eating behavior and appetite
Eating behavior : rating satiety	Observation observation_concept_id 4326261 Satiety
Eating behavior : rating satiety	Observation observation_concept_id 4326261 Satiety
Eating behavior : rating satiety	Observation observation_concept_id 4326261 Satiety
Eating behavior : rating satiety	Observation observation_concept_id 4326261 Satiety
Eating behavior : rating satiety	Observation observation_concept_id 4326261 Satiety
Family history : number of diabetic children	Observation observation_concept_id 4334340 Family history of diabetes mellitus in first-degree relative
Family history : number of diabetic children	Observation observation_concept_id 4334340 Family history of diabetes mellitus type 2
Family history : number of diabetic children	Observation observation_concept_id 4334340 Family history of diabetes mellitus type 2
Family history : number of diabetic children	Observation observation_concept_id 4334340 Family history of diabetes mellitus type 2
Family history : number of diabetic children	Observation observation_concept_id 4334340 Family history of diabetes mellitus type 2
Family history : number of diabetic children	Observation observation_concept_id 4334340 Family history of diabetes mellitus in child of subject
Family history : number of diabetic sisters	Observation observation_concept_id 4334340 Family history of diabetes mellitus type 2
Family history : number of obese brothers	Observation observation_concept_id 4051566 FH: Obesity

Main issues

- Process of harmonisation is largely manual and time consuming
- Harmonisation needs to be done on multiple projects in parallel with limited resources
- Cohorts/datasets often end up differently harmonised – need to harmonise the harmonisation 😊

Ontomapper for clinical term harmonisation

Lou Götz
(SIB)

Onto-Mapper Welcome Mark Ibberson

Welcome to Onto-Mapper

Cardiateam

Assessment of the uniqueness of diabetic cardiomyopathy relative to other forms of heart failure using unbiased phenotyping approaches

1 cohort

CARDIATEAM

Endotarget

ENDOTARGET explores the relationship between gut microbiota, gut permeability, and systemic endotoxemia with a special focus on the three most abundant rheumatic diseases (RDs): osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis and spondylarthritis.

6 cohorts

BIOMARKERS_24_08_15 ENDOTARGET ESTBB_24_08_15 ESTBB_24_09_20 FINRISK_24_08_15
FINRISK_24_08_30

Hippocrates

Health initiatives in Psoriasis and PsOlastic arthritis Consortium European States

7 cohorts

BIOCOM BIOCOM_22_03_2024 CIMD GLOSSARY OUTPASS SOPHOS XGITING

Obelisk

Preventing childhood obesity to stay healthy throughout life

12 cohorts

CHILDHOOD OBESITY GROUP-MESSINA ELIPSE FINNGEDI GOOD IT-PRECLMED-VR MOLGENIS
MOLGENIS_NEW NFBC1966 NFBC1996 OBE-RARE OFFSPRING OF MOTHER WITH GDM TOPS

Sophia

Stratification of obese phenotypes to optimize future obesity therapy

16 cohorts

ABDS ACCELERATE ADJUNCT APY BI POOLED TRIALS COLAUS DPV EXTEND NOK
REVIND ROTTERDAM SCALE DM SCALE M SCALE OP SCALE SA TAYSIDE

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Ontomapper for clinical term harmonisation

Lou Götz
(SIB)

The screenshot shows the Ontomapper web application interface. At the top, the title is "Cardiateam (Cardiateam) - Biological Parameters". Below the title, there are tabs for "ALL", "UNMAPPED", and "MAPPED". A "DOWNLOAD MAPPING" button is visible in the top right corner.

The main content area is titled "49 fields" and includes an "Advanced filters" section. The filters are categorized as follows:

- Color by:** Domain (selected), Concept status
- Domains:** Observation (blue), Drug (purple), Device (green), Condition (pink), Measurement (orange), Procedure (light green), Others (grey)
- Ontologies:** LOINC (blue), SNOMEDCT (light blue), RXNORM (dark blue), Standard (grey)
- Suggestions from:** TextTerm (grey), Other cohorts (orange)

The main table displays a list of fields with their corresponding LOINC and SNOMEDCT codes and status. The table has two columns: "filter by name" and "filter by concept_id".

filter by name	*	filter by concept_id
?_qt	* LOINC	Normal glucose tolerance (Erythrocyte activity/volume) in Serum or Plasma
alat	* LOINC	Alanine aminotransferase (Erythrocyte activity/volume) in Serum or Plasma
albumin	* SNOMEDCT	Serum albumin level
	* LOINC	Albumin (Mass/volume) in Urine
albumin to creatinine ratio	* LOINC	Albumin/Creatinine Ratio in Urine
	* SNOMEDCT	Urine albumin/creatinine ratio measurement
alp	* LOINC	Alkaline phosphatase (Erythrocyte activity/volume) in Serum
asat	* LOINC	Aspartate aminotransferase (Erythrocyte activity/volume) in Serum or Plasma
bilirubin	* LOINC	Bilirubin total (Mass/volume) in Serum or Plasma
	* SNOMEDCT	Serum bilirubin level
c_peptide	* LOINC	C-peptide (Mass/volume) in Serum or Plasma
	* SNOMEDCT	Serum C-peptide measurement
ca	* LOINC	Calcium (Mass/volume) in Serum
	* SNOMEDCT	Serum calcium level
cholesterol total	* LOINC	Cholesterol (Mass/volume) in Serum or Plasma
ck-nac activity	*	
cl	* LOINC	Chloride (Mass/volume) in Serum or Plasma
	* SNOMEDCT	Serum chloride level

Ontomapper - harmonised variables across cohorts

Lou Götz
(SIB)

LLMs for improved concept mapping

Imane Lboukili
(SIB)

LLMs for improved concept mapping

Imane Lboukili
(SIB)

1- SNOMED data preparation

Concatenate all related concepts in one row.

2- Embeddings creation

Using Open AI embeddings model (3-large), create embeddings: high-dimensional **numeric vector representations** of the SNOMED CT data, which capture semantic context.

3- Vector store creation

An **optimized storage** and querying abilities tailored for the distinct nature of vector embeddings.

4- Score (cosine similarity) calculation

Measures the similarity between the **query** and the **available embeddings** in the vector store to determine the closest term(s)/concept(s).

Demo

<https://ontomapper.vital-it.ch/>

Thank you

DATA SCIENTISTS FOR LIFE

sib.swiss

Group work – Solutions for metadata improvement

Challenges

 BeeBiome All data ▾ Advanced search Wiki ▾ Help ▾ About ▾

BeeBiome browse table

This browse interface allows to discover BeeBiome data. A basic search (on all fields) is available at top right of the table. An [advanced search](#) is available to do a search on each field. More details on each field are available in our [help page](#).

Results are ordered by 'BioProject acc.', then 'BioSample acc.'. The order could be changed by clicking on one column, then press shift and click on another column. Clicking on the '+' sign shows the full information for each sample.

Show entries Showing 1 to 10 of 32,310 entries Filter:

	BioProject acc. ▲	BioSample acc. ▲	SRA experiment entries ▾	NCBI Nucleotide entries ▾	Host ▾	Organism ▾	Collection date ▾	Geo. location name ▾	Library source(s) ▾	Library layout(s) ▾	Library strategy(ies) ▾
	PRJDB11061	SAMD00272082	1	0	Tetragonula	insect gut metagenome	2017-04-22	Philippines:Bicol Region, Camarines Sur, Buhi	METAGENOMIC	PAIRED	AMPLICON
Instrument(s) Illumina MiSeq											
Center name Functional Genomics Laboratory, National Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, University of the Philippines Diliman											
BioSample package acc. MIMARKS.specimen.host-associated.6.0											
	PRJDB11061	SAMD00272083	1	0	Tetragonula	insect gut metagenome	2017-04-22	Philippines:Bicol Region, Sorsogon, Bulusan	METAGENOMIC	PAIRED	AMPLICON
	PRJDB11061	SAMD00272084	1	0	Tetragonula	insect gut metagenome	2017-04-22	Philippines:Bicol Region, Camarines Sur, Caramoan	METAGENOMIC	PAIRED	AMPLICON
	PRJDB11061	SAMD00272085	1	0	Tetragonula	insect gut metagenome	2017-04-22	Philippines:Bicol Region, Camarines Sur, Caramoan	METAGENOMIC	PAIRED	AMPLICON

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Show 10 ▾ entries Showing 1 to 10 of 32,310 entries Filter:

BioProject acc.	BioSample acc.	SRA experiment entries	NCBI Nucleotide entries	Host	Organism	Collection	Geo.	Experiment	Library	Strategy
PRJDB11061	SAMD00272082	1	0	Tetragonula	insect gut metagenome	2017-04-22	Philippines:Bicol Region, Sorsogon, Bulusan	METAGENOMIC	PAIRED	AMPLICON
PRJDB11061	SAMD00272083	1	0	Tetragonula	insect gut metagenome	2017-04-22	Philippines:Bicol Region, Sorsogon, Bulusan	METAGENOMIC	PAIRED	AMPLICON
PRJDB11061	SAMD00272084	1	0	Tetragonula	insect gut metagenome	2017-04-22	Philippines:Bicol Region, Camarines Sur, Caramoan	METAGENOMIC	PAIRED	AMPLICON
PRJDB11061	SAMD00272085	1	0	Tetragonula	insect gut metagenome	2017-04-22	Philippines:Bicol Region, Camarines Sur, Caramoan	METAGENOMIC	PAIRED	AMPLICON

What are the possible solutions to improve metadata?

Group work – Solutions for metadata improvement

Group 1 [Onsite]: Before submission - how to encourage better metadata submission?

Facilitators: Espen - Secretary: Bérénice

Group work 2 [Onsite]: After submission - how to expand and curate existing metadata?

Facilitators: Sara - Secretary: Erik

Group work 3 [Online]: After submission - how to expand and curate existing metadata?

Facilitators: Nikolaos

Summary & Closing

Report on F1000

- Anyone wants to contribute?
- Add your details

List of participants (Please fill in):

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